

I am S [REDACTED] A [REDACTED] a Ghanaian /Tafo.

Speaking from Belgium in a manner of stranded, which is not supposed to be as a Ghanaian but I found myself in. Why??

Which is because this 21st century still you those we called our leaders don't know the world is moving forward. That's not the reason I'm writing to you.

I hope you guys know human rights very well? Then please kindly cancel bill against LGBT +Q. Because it is our life not yours. Love is love and each and every one has the right to love period.

#KILLTHEBILL.

KILL THE BILL AGAINST SAME SEX IN GHANA. There's a saying home sweet home but the 1960 criminal code article 29 section 104 is threatening and making home bitter for and any LGBT +Q in Ghana we're pleading, consider equality.

There's a saying life is beautiful.....

How can life will be beautiful without living the kind life you want?

#KILLTHEBILL and LEGALISED SAME SAME.